

Understanding Morphea: Insights into Localized Scleroderma

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Abstract:

Morphea, or localized scleroderma, is a rare inflammatory connective tissue disorder characterized by skin thickening and fibrosis. This review provides an overview of morphea, including its epidemiology, pathogenesis, clinical types, diagnosis, and treatment options. Morphea predominantly affects children and women, with peaks in early childhood and the fifth decade of life. The disease involves genetic, environmental, and immune factors, leading to increased collagen production. Clinical forms include limited, generalized, linear, mixed, and pansclerotic types. Diagnosis is clinical, supported by histopathology and imaging. Treatment is individualized, involving topical therapies (corticosteroids, tacrolimus), systemic therapies (methotrexate, corticosteroids), and phototherapy (UVA, PUVA). Emerging therapies targeting specific pathways show promise. In children, early aggressive treatment is crucial to prevent complications. Postirradiation morphea and variants like keloid morphea require accurate diagnosis for appropriate management. Phototherapy, particularly low-dose UVA, is effective. Early diagnosis and tailored treatment are essential for managing morphea and preventing long-term complications.

Keywords: Morphea, Localized Scleroderma, Epidemiology, Pathogenesis, clinical types, Diagnosis, Treatment options.

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Introduction

Morphea, a term used in preference to 'localized scleroderma', encompasses a group of related conditions in which inflammation drives fibrosis and which are characterized by varying degrees of inflammation, fibrosis, sclerosis and atrophy in the skin and subcutaneous tissues, sometimes extending deeply into muscle, bone, eye and brain.

Unlike systemic sclerosis, morphea is typically confined to the skin and underlying tissues, without internal organ involvement. The disease can lead to significant cosmetic and functional impairments, affecting the quality of life of those diagnosed. Morphea predominantly affects children and women, with two peaks in incidence observed: early childhood and the fifth decade of life [1]. The overall female-to-male ratio is approximately 4:1 [2,3]. The pathogenesis of morphea is complex and not fully understood. It is believed to involve a combi-

nation of genetic predisposition, environmental triggers, and immune system dysregulation. Key cytokines and growth factors, such as transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β), interleukin-4 (IL-4), and interleukin-6 (IL-6), play significant roles in the disease process by promoting collagen production and fibrosis [4]. The disease progresses through three phases: early inflammatory, fibrotic/sclerotic, and atrophic, each with distinct clinical and histopathological features.

Clinically, morphea can present in various forms, including limited, generalized, linear, mixed, and pansclerotic types. Limited morphea involves a few patches on the trunk or limbs, while generalized morphea affects multiple areas. Linear morphea is characterized by lines of involvement on the limbs or head, often leading to significant functional impairment. Mixed morphea combines features of

circumscribed and linear or generalized and linear types, and pansclerotic morphea involves all the skin, potentially leading to severe disability [5]. Diagnosis of morphea is primarily clinical, supported by histopathological examination and imaging techniques such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and ultrasonography. Key diagnostic features include thickened collagen bundles in the dermis and subcutaneous tissues, with varying degrees of inflammation [6].

Treatment of morphea is individualized based on the type and severity of the disease. Common treatment options include topical therapies (corticosteroids, tacrolimus, and vitamin D analogues), systemic therapies (methotrexate, corticosteroids, and mycophenolate mofetil), and phototherapy (UVA and PUVA). Emerging therapies targeting specific inflammatory and fibrotic pathways, such as TGF- β inhibitors and Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors, show promise in improving patient outcomes [7].

In pediatric cases, early and aggressive treatment is crucial to prevent complications such as growth retardation and joint contractures. Long-term follow-up is essential to monitor for disease recurrence and manage any residual effects [8]. Postirradiation morphea, a rare phenomenon occurring after radiation therapy, often in breast cancer patients, can present with features similar to idiopathic morphea and may be associated with other autoimmune phenomena, such as subcutaneous polyarteritis nodosa [9].

Keloid morphea and nodular scleroderma are distinct clinical variants of scleroderma, requiring accurate diagnosis for appropriate treatment. Phototherapy, particularly low-dose UVA, has been shown to be effective in treating morphea, with studies demonstrating that lower doses are as beneficial as higher doses [10].

Morphea is a complex and heterogeneous disease with various clinical presentations and treatment challenges. Early diagnosis and individualized treatment are crucial for managing the disease and preventing long-term complications. Ongoing research into the pathogenesis and emerging therapies holds promise for improving outcomes for patients with morphea.

Epidemiology

The annual incidence of morphea varies widely, ranging from 4 to 27 new cases per million people [11,12]. This variation in incidence may be attributed to differences in diagnostic criteria, reporting practices, and population demographics across different regions. Morphea predominantly affects children and women, with two distinct peaks in incidence. The first peak occurs in early childhood, typically between the ages of 2 and 14, while the

second peak is observed in the fifth decade of life [2]. The disease exhibits a marked female preponderance, with an overall female-to-male ratio of approximately 4:1 [13,14]. This gender disparity suggests that hormonal factors may play a role in the pathogenesis of the disease.

The exact prevalence of morphea is difficult to determine due to its rarity and the variability in clinical presentation. However, it is estimated that morphea accounts for about 2.7% of all cases of scleroderma [5]. The disease can occur at any age, but the majority of cases are diagnosed in children and young adults.

Geographically, morphea appears to have a higher prevalence in certain populations. Studies have shown that Caucasians are more commonly affected than other racial groups [6]. However, the reasons for this racial predilection are not well understood and may involve genetic, environmental, and socioeconomic factors.

In terms of familial occurrence, morphea is generally considered to be sporadic, with only a small percentage of cases showing a familial pattern. This suggests that while genetic factors may contribute to the susceptibility to morphea, environmental triggers are likely to play a significant role in the onset of the disease [4].

Overall, the epidemiology of morphea highlights the importance of early recognition and diagnosis, particularly in high-risk populations such as children and women. Understanding the demographic and geographic patterns of morphea can aid in the development of targeted public health strategies and improve patient outcomes through timely intervention and management.

Pathogenesis

The pathogenesis of morphea, or localized scleroderma, is complex and multifactorial, involving genetic predisposition, environmental triggers, and immune system dysregulation. Although the exact mechanisms remain unclear, several key factors have been identified that contribute to the development and progression of the disease.

Genetic factors play a significant role in the susceptibility to morphea. Studies have shown that certain human leukocyte antigen (HLA) alleles are associated with an increased risk of developing the disease. Additionally, familial cases of morphea, although rare, suggest a genetic component to disease susceptibility [4].

Environmental triggers are also implicated in the pathogenesis of morphea. Trauma, infections, and radiation therapy have been reported as potential initiating factors. For instance, postirradiation morphea is a recognized phenomenon, particularly in breast cancer patients who have undergone radi-

tion therapy [9]. These environmental factors may act as triggers in genetically predisposed individuals, leading to the activation of the disease process.

Immune system dysregulation is a central feature of morphea. The disease is characterized by an abnormal immune response, with increased activity of T-helper cells and the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Key cytokines involved in the pathogenesis of morphea include transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β), interleukin-4 (IL-4), and interleukin-6 (IL-6). These cytokines promote the activation of fibroblasts and the excessive production of collagen, leading to skin thickening and fibrosis [4,5].

The disease progresses through three phases:

Early inflammatory phase, there is an influx of inflammatory cells, including lymphocytes and macrophages, into the affected skin clinically manifested as a subtle bruise like appearance. This is followed by the fibrotic/sclerotic phase, characterized by the activation of fibroblasts and the deposition of excessive collagen in the dermis and subcutaneous tissues seen clinically as a waxy, yellowish white area surrounded by an erythematous to violaceous so-called 'lilac ring'. In the atrophic phase, there is a loss of adnexal structures and thinning of the skin, leading to atrophy and potential functional impairment [6]. In some cases, no sclerotic phase is seen and lesions progress straight to the atrophic hyperpigmented stage.

Overall, the pathogenesis of morphea involves a complex interplay of genetic, environmental, and immunological factors. Understanding these mechanisms is crucial for developing targeted therapies that can effectively manage and treat the disease [15,16].

Clinical Types of Morphea

Morphea, or localized scleroderma, presents in various clinical forms, each with distinct characteristics and implications for treatment and prognosis. The primary clinical types of morphea include:

1. Limited Morphea: This form is characterized by a few well-defined patches of thickened, sclerotic skin, typically located on the trunk or limbs. These patches are often oval or round and may be associated with changes in skin color, such as hyperpigmentation or hypopigmentation.

It is subdivided into:

- **Circumscribed plaque morphea (commonest)**

Single or multiple, round to oval lesions >1cm in diameter, in up to two of seven anatomical regions (head-neck, each limb, anterior trunk, posterior trunk).

Changes limited to the epidermis and dermis -
CIRCUMSCRIBED SUPERFICIAL PLAQUE MORPHEA

Extension to the subcutis, fascia and underlying muscle-
CIRCUMSCRIBED DEEP PLAQUE MORPHEA [17,18].

- **Guttate morphea**

Multiple, small (<1cm) erythematous or yellowish white, mildly indurated lesions, shiny, crinkled surface, mostly affecting Children. Most common site: trunk [17,18].

- **Atrophoderma of Pasini-Pierini**

Non-indurated, blue-grey to brown, hyperpigmented and sharply demarcated depressed patches with visible vessels, with a 'cliff-drop' edge. It might be distributed in 'symmetric' or 'zosteriform' pattern [17,18].

2. Generalized Morphea: In this type, multiple patches of morphea distributed across a broader area of the body, can coalesce, leading to extensive areas of skin involvement and significant cosmetic and functional impairment.

Several definitions have been provided, as follows:

- Falanga: ≥ 5 lesions, B/L lesions and evidence of joining together of ≥ 2 individual patches
- PRES classification: Induration of the skin starting ≥ 4 individual plaques, > 3cm, that become confluent and involve ≥ 2 out of 7 anatomical sites (head-neck, right upper extremity, left upper extremity, right lower extremity, left lower extremity, anterior trunk, posterior trunk)
- Plaques involving ≥ 3 of these same 7 anatomical sites.

It has two subsets:

Isomorphic: Areas of morphea are along the bra-line and waistband, bilateral inguinal areas and a diamond-shaped region over the mid-lower back. Koebnerisation of lesions can be seen into sites of low-level trauma from clothing. Overlying lichen sclerosis is common

Symmetric: Typically affects a butterfly-shaped area on the lower abdomen below the umbilicus, the anterior tibia, popliteal and antecubital fossae, and arcuate areas on the breasts sparing the areolae. It has higher prevalence of associated autoimmunity. [11,19]

3. Linear Morphea: This form is marked by linear bands of sclerotic skin, commonly affecting the limbs or face.

Trunk / Limb Variant (more common)

Linear Morphea: Linear bands following Blaschko lines may appear suddenly or insidiously and then progress in a piecemeal linear fashion along a limb and then coalesce over time to form a more obvious linear band. Lesions extending across joints result in flexion contractures or limited range of motion and limb asymmetry/shortening

Linear Atrophoderma of Moulin: Unilateral, depressed, hyperpigmented Blaschkoid lesions on the trunk and limbs, with onset between 6 and 20 years of age

Linear Deep Atrophic Morphea: Linear primary atrophic morphea with no preceding clinical inflammation or sclerosis. Although progressive in nature, they do not result in joint contractures. [17,18]

Head / Neck Variant:

Morphea en coup de sabre: Typically presents as a linear band which involves the paramedian forehead and/or the frontoparietal scalp and follows Blaschko lines. Alopecia of the eyelashes, eyebrows and scalp occur if they are involved in the band (usually irreversible)

Progressive hemifacial atrophy/Parry Romberg Syndrome: Unilateral, progressive disorder developing as a result of a gradual loss of subcutaneous tissue and muscle, and atrophy of the frontal, maxillary and/or mandibular bones. Deviation of mouth, nose towards the affected side, dental malocclusion and hemiatrophy of the tongue occurs. [17,18]

4. Mixed Morphea: Patients with mixed morphea exhibit features of both circumscribed and linear morphea. This type can present a combination of patches and linear bands, complicating the clinical picture and management.

5. Pansclerotic Morphea: Extensive, often circumferential involvement of the majority of body surface areas with sparing of the fingers and toes, affecting all layers of skin to involve muscle, tendon and bones. Notoriously known for being resistant to treatment, pansclerotic morphea can lead to severe disability due to extensive skin thickening and fibrosis, ulceration which can transform into Squamous cell carcinoma, affecting mobility and overall function. [17,18]

6. Eosinophilic fasciitis: Usually extensive and involves deep tissues, symmetrically involving the extremities, particularly the lower limbs causing woody hard, but typically spares the fingers and face. There is induration and fibrosis causing puckering and peau d' orange appearance with tethering around vessels producing guttering referred to as groove sign. [17]

1. Morphea-lichen sclerosis overlap
2. Disease modifiers:

Deep Morphea/ Morphoes Profunda: Inflammation and sclerosis are found in the deep dermis, panniculus, fascia or muscle. It is characterized by firm to hard, bound down to underlying structures, edges may be less well defined, the overlying skin puckered, have a cobblestone or peau d'orange appearance

Bullous: This form of morphea has tense subepidermal bullae on a background of typical morphea

Cause of bullae:

- ✓ subepidermal oedema induced by lymphangiectasias secondary to dermal sclerosis
- ✓ excessive skin trauma or friction at susceptible sites

Keloidal / Nodular: It presents as keloidal growths in patients with previous or coexistent morphea, more in patients with ISSc, more common on the upper body where they may coalesce or occur in a linear pattern. [17,18,20] Understanding the clinical types of morphea is crucial for accurate diagnosis and tailored treatment, as each type presents unique challenges and requires specific management strategies [9,19,21].

Diagnosis of Morphea

The diagnosis of morphea, or localized scleroderma, is primarily clinical, supported by histopathological examination and imaging techniques. Early and accurate diagnosis is crucial for effective management and prevention of long-term complications.

Clinical Evaluation: The initial diagnosis of morphea is based on a thorough clinical examination. Key clinical features include well-defined patches of thickened, sclerotic skin that may be hyperpigmented or hypopigmented. The distribution and morphology of the lesions help differentiate between the various clinical types of morphea, such as limited, generalized, linear, mixed, and pansclerotic forms [5].

Histopathological Examination: A skin biopsy is often performed to confirm the diagnosis and assess the extent of fibrosis. Histopathological findings in morphea include thickened collagen bundles in the dermis and subcutaneous tissues, with varying degrees of inflammation. In the early inflammatory phase, there is a perivascular and interstitial infiltrate of lymphocytes and plasma cells [6]. Instead of lying near the dermal-subcutaneous junction as in normal skin, eccrine glands appear higher in the dermis as a result of the replacement of most of the subcutaneous fat by newly formed collagen [18,22]. As the disease progresses to the fibrotic/sclerotic phase, the collagen bundles become more densely packed, and adnexal structures may be lost. In the atrophic phase, there is thinning of the skin and loss of adnexal structures [6].

Imaging Techniques: Imaging modalities such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), ultrasonography, durometry, goniometry can be useful in assessing the depth and activity of the lesions and joint contracture. MRI is particularly helpful in evaluating deep morphea and detecting involvement of underlying structures such as muscles and bones. Ultrasonography can provide real-time assessment of skin thickness and vascularity, aiding in the monitoring of disease progression and response to treatment [6,17].

Laboratory Tests: Although there are no specific laboratory tests for morphea, certain tests can help rule out other conditions and assess the overall health of the patient. These may include complete blood count, liver and kidney function tests, thyroid profile, serum immunoglobulins, ESR/CRP, CK, lactase dehydrogenase and/or aldolase, borrelia serology and autoantibody screening. Elevated levels of antinuclear antibodies (ANA) and other autoantibodies may be present in some patients, particularly those with generalized or linear morphea [4, 17, 23].

Treatment of Morphea

Morphea, or localized scleroderma, is a challenging condition to manage due to its heterogeneous nature and varying degrees of severity. The primary goals of treatment are to halt disease progression, alleviate symptoms, and prevent complications such as joint contractures and cosmetic disfigurement. Treatment strategies are tailored to the type and severity of morphea, and may include topical therapies, systemic medications, and phototherapy. Emerging therapies targeting specific pathways involved in the disease process also show promise.

Topical Therapies

Corticosteroids: Topical corticosteroids are commonly used as first-line treatment for localized and less severe forms of morphea. They help reduce inflammation and slow the progression of skin thickening. High-potency corticosteroids, such as clobetasol propionate, are often applied to affected areas once or twice daily. However, long-term use of topical corticosteroids can lead to skin atrophy and other side effects, so their use is typically limited to short courses [11,15,24].

Calcineurin Inhibitors: Topical calcineurin inhibitors, such as tacrolimus and pimecrolimus, are alternatives to corticosteroids, particularly for sensitive areas like the face. These agents modulate the immune response and have been shown to be effective in reducing inflammation and skin thickening in morphea. Tacrolimus 0.1% ointment, applied twice daily, has demonstrated efficacy in clinical studies [12,13,14].

Vitamin D Analogues: Topical vitamin D analogues, such as calcipotriol, have also been used in the treatment of morphea. These agents inhibit fibroblast proliferation and collagen production, helping to reduce skin thickening. Calcipotriol is often used in combination with topical corticosteroids to enhance efficacy [25,26,27].

5% Imiquimod cream, Pirfenidone 8% gel, Tranilast (N-[3,4-dimethoxy cinnamoyl]-anthranilic acid) are newer topical modalities in practice [17].

Systemic Therapies

Methotrexate: Methotrexate is a cornerstone of systemic therapy for moderate to severe morphea, particularly in cases with deep tissue involvement or rapid progression. It is an immunosuppressive agent that inhibits the proliferation of inflammatory cells and fibroblasts. Methotrexate is typically administered orally or subcutaneously at a dose of 15-25 mg per week. It is often combined with systemic corticosteroids to achieve better control of the disease [6].

Corticosteroids: Systemic corticosteroids, such as prednisone, are used in combination with methotrexate for their potent anti-inflammatory effects. They are particularly useful in the early stages of treatment to rapidly control inflammation and prevent further tissue damage. The dosage and duration of corticosteroid therapy are carefully monitored to minimize side effects [11,15,24].

Mycophenolate Mofetil: Mycophenolate mofetil is another immunosuppressive agent used in the treatment of morphea, especially in patients who do not respond to methotrexate. It inhibits the proliferation of lymphocytes and reduces the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Mycophenolate mofetil is typically administered at a dose of 1-2 grams per day, divided into two doses [28,29].

Phototherapy

Ultraviolet A (UVA) and PUVA Therapy: Phototherapy, particularly UVA and psoralen plus UVA (PUVA) therapy, has been shown to be effective in treating morphea. UVA therapy involves exposing the affected skin to ultraviolet A light, which helps reduce skin thickening and inflammation. PUVA therapy combines UVA exposure with the administration of psoralen, a photosensitizing agent, to enhance the therapeutic effects. Studies have demonstrated that low-dose UVA phototherapy (5, 10, and 20 J/cm²) is beneficial in treating both morphea and systemic sclerosis, with lower doses being as effective as higher doses [10].

Emerging Therapies

Biologic Agents: Emerging therapies targeting specific pathways involved in the pathogenesis of morphea show promise. Biologic agents, such as tocilizumab (an IL-6 receptor antagonist) and rituximab (an anti-CD20 monoclonal antibody), have been explored in clinical trials. These agents target specific components of the immune system, potentially offering more targeted and effective treatment options for morphea [7].

Antifibrotic Agents: Antifibrotic agents, such as imatinib (a tyrosine kinase inhibitor) and pirfenidone, are being investigated for their potential to reduce fibrosis in morphea. These agents inhibit the signaling pathways involved in fibroblast activation and collagen production, thereby reducing skin thickening and improving skin texture [7].

Multidisciplinary Approach

The management of morphea often requires a multidisciplinary approach involving dermatologists, rheumatologists, and physical therapists. Tendon lengthening, autologous fat transplantation, implantation of fillers are few surgical approaches for managing contractures and physical disabilities. Physical therapy is essential for maintaining joint mobility and preventing contractures, particularly in patients with linear morphea affecting the limbs. Regular follow-up and monitoring are crucial to assess treatment response and adjust therapy as needed [17,30].

Discussion

Morphea, or localized scleroderma, presents a significant clinical challenge due to its diverse manifestations and potential for severe morbidity. This review has highlighted the importance of a comprehensive and individualized approach to the diagnosis and management of morphea, emphasizing the need for early intervention and tailored treatment strategies.

The variability in clinical presentation, ranging from limited patches to extensive skin involvement, necessitates a nuanced understanding of the disease. Accurate diagnosis, supported by histopathological examination and advanced imaging techniques, is crucial for determining the extent of the disease and guiding appropriate treatment decisions.

Topical therapies, including corticosteroids, calcineurin inhibitors, and vitamin D analogues, remain essential for managing localized and less severe forms of morphea. For more extensive or rapidly progressing cases, systemic therapies such as methotrexate, corticosteroids, and mycophenolate mofetil are indispensable. Phototherapy, particularly UVA and PUVA, has proven effective in reducing skin thickening and inflammation, offering a valuable treatment option for many patients.

Emerging therapies targeting specific pathways involved in the pathogenesis of morphea, such as biologic agents and antifibrotic drugs, represent a promising frontier in the management of this condition. These novel treatments have the potential to provide more targeted and effective options for patients with refractory disease, improving outcomes and quality of life. A multidisciplinary approach is often necessary to address the diverse clinical manifestations of morphea. Collaboration between dermatologists, rheumatologists, and physical therapists is essential for comprehensive care, particularly in managing complications such as joint contractures and functional impairments.

In pediatric cases, early and aggressive treatment is paramount to prevent long-term complications and ensure optimal growth and development. Regular follow-up and monitoring are critical to assess treatment response and adjust therapy as needed.

Overall, the management of morphea requires a dynamic and evolving approach, informed by ongoing research and clinical advancements. Continued investigation into the underlying mechanisms and novel therapeutic strategies will be key to improving the care and outcomes for patients with morphea. By fostering a deeper understanding of this complex disorder, we can enhance our ability to provide effective and compassionate care to those affected by morphea.

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